

ISic2764

I.Sicily inscription 2764

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

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Autopsy

July 2006 and checked 30.09.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Foundations of a house to the NE of Chiesa di S.Lucia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 30830

Physical Description

A small quadrangular limestone altar, with a square base and worn/rounded upper corners on the plain upper section; the upper edge is worn away

Dimensions

Height 9 cm

Width 8.5 cm

Depth 7.5 cm

Layout

Three lines of Greek letters, of which the first line is in much smaller than the second two and partly worn away

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Lunate sigma and omega; zeta employs elegant curved strokes. Text is carelessly set out, with sigma on line two running to the edge and the upsilon of line 3 squeezed into the remaining space.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 4 mm

Lines 2-3: 17 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Z]ωσίμου[ς]

2. Ζωσ

3. ίμου

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Zosimos son of Zosimos

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645161

PHI 332966

Bibliography

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014